

**TRANSIENT ANALYSIS OF A CRACK IN A COMPOSITE LAYERED
MEDIUM SUBJECTED TO DYNAMIC LOADINGS**

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a semi-infinite crack in a layered medium subjected to antiplane dynamic loading is investigated. In analyzing this problem, the reflections and diffractions of stress waves by the interface boundary and by the crack will generate an infinite number of waves, must be taken into account. A useful fundamental solution is proposed in this study and the solution is determined by superposition of the fundamental solution in the Laplace transform domain. The final formulations for stress intensity factor are expressed explicitly and the dynamic effect of each wave is presented in a closed form.

INTRODUCTION

In conventional studies of a semi-infinite crack in an unbounded medium subjected to dynamic loading, the complete solution is obtained by integral transform methods together with direct application of the Wiener-Hopf technique (Noble [1]) and the Cagniard-de Hoop method (de Hoop [2]) of Laplace inversion. If the loading is replaced by a nonuniform distribution having a characteristic length, then the same procedure using integral transformation methods does not apply. The problem of an elastic solid containing a semi-infinite crack subjected to concentrated point loading on the faces of the crack has been previously studied by Freund [3]. He proposed a fundamental solution arising from an edge dislocation climbing along the line ahead of the crack tip with a constant speed to overcome these difficulties of the case with a characteristic length. The solution can be constructed by taking an integration over a climbing dislocation of different moving velocity. A thorough summary of the application of the main direct methods of analysis for transient problem in dynamic fracture for elastic or inelastic problems has been given by Freund [4].

Most of the solved dynamic fracture problems are regarded as a crack subjected to applying a uniformly distributed dynamic loading on the crack faces or subjected to incident plane waves. For the above mentioned problems, either the direct application of the well known Wiener-Hopf technique is used or the superposition method proposed by Freund is performed to solve the problems. However, if a crack is subjected to incident nonplanar waves, none of the known methods can be used to obtain the transient solutions. Recently Tsai and Ma [5] proposed a new fundamental solution to overcome these difficulties. The fundamental problem they considered is an exponentially distributed traction applied on crack faces and the solution is constructed by superposition of the fundamental solution in the Laplace transform domain. Tsai and Ma [5] used this new fundamental solution to obtain the transient solution for a stationary semi-infinite crack subjected to a suddenly applied dynamic inplane body force in an unbounded medium. This alternative fundamental solution is also successfully applied towards solving more complicated transient prob-

lems (Tsai and Ma, [6], [7], and Ma and Chen, [8]) for a subsurface stationary inclined crack subjected to dynamic loadings.

Determination of the dependence of the dynamic stress intensity factor on body configuration and applied loading is a principal objective in dynamic fracture. The problem considered in this study is a horizontal semi-infinite crack in a strip with finite width for a layered medium as shown in Fig. 1. In analyzing the above mentioned problems, the interface boundary and crack are considered into the analysis. The interaction of the reflected waves generated from the interface boundary and the crack must be taken into account which will make the analysis extremely difficult. It is impossible to solve this complicated problem by using the standard Wiener-Hopf technique and some other approach must be followed. A useful fundamental solution is proposed to overcome these difficulties. This proposed fundamental solution is successfully applied towards solving the problem and is demonstrated as an efficient methodology to solve similar problems. Since the stress intensity factor is the key parameter in characterizing dynamic crack grows, we will focus our attention mainly on the determination of the dynamic stress intensity factor.

REQUIRED FUNDAMENTAL SOLUTIONS

As usual in problems of the type considered here, superposition of solutions plays a significant role. The solutions of the problem considered in this study can be determined by superposition of the following problems. Problem A treats a dynamic concentrated loading acting on semi-infinite crack faces in an unbounded medium at time $t = 0$, which induces incident waves propagating toward the plane that will eventually define the interface boundary. In problem B, a semi-infinite interface is considered in which the boundary is subjected to incident waves which are equal to the corresponding waves generated from the crack tip in problem A. Problem C considers an infinite body containing a semi-infinite crack in which the crack is subjected to the reflected waves which are generated by the interface boundary in problem B. The three fundamental problems A, B and C are superimposed to obtain the solution for a crack interaction with stress waves.

Problem C in the aforementioned three fundamental problems is the only one which needs careful analysis. The problem we will deal with is the interaction of the propagating crack with cylindrical reflected waves, which causes the only difficulty in this investigation. The superposition scheme proposed in this study, unlike usual superposition methods which are performed in the time domain, is performed in the Laplace transform domain.

Consider the fundamental problem of antiplane deformation for a semi-infinite crack in an unbounded medium. The problem can be viewed as a half-plane problem with the material occupying the region $y \geq 0$, subjected to the following mixed boundary conditions in the Laplace transform domain

$$\bar{\tau}_{yz}(x, 0, s) = e^{\eta x} \quad -\infty < x < 0, \tag{2.1}$$

$$\bar{w}(x, 0, s) = 0 \quad 0 < x < \infty, \tag{2.2}$$

where s is the Laplace transform parameter and η is a constant. The overbar symbol is used for denoting the transform on time t . This fundamental problem can be solved by using the standard transform method and the Wiener-Hopf technique. The governing equation can be represented by the two-dimensional wave equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} = b^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2}, \tag{2.3}$$

where b is the slowness of the shear wave given by

$$b = 1/v_s = \sqrt{\rho/\mu},$$

in which $w(x, y, t)$ is the displacement normal to the xy -plane; v_s is the shear wave speed, μ and ρ are the respective shear modulus and the mass density of the material. The nonvanishing shear stresses are

$$\tau_{yz} = \mu \frac{\partial w}{\partial y}, \quad \tau_{xz} = \mu \frac{\partial w}{\partial x}. \tag{2.4}$$

The solutions of stresses and displacement for the boundary conditions (2.1) and (2.2) expressed in the transform domain are

$$\bar{r}_{yz}(x, y, s) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_\lambda} \frac{(b + \lambda)^{1/2} e^{-s(\alpha y - \lambda x)}}{(b + \eta)^{1/2} (\eta - \lambda)} d\lambda, \quad (2.5)$$

$$\bar{r}_{xz}(x, y, s) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_\lambda} \frac{\lambda e^{-s(\alpha y - \lambda x)}}{(b + \eta)^{1/2} (\eta - \lambda)(b - \lambda)^{1/2}} d\lambda, \quad (2.6)$$

$$\bar{w}(x, y, s) = -\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_\lambda} \frac{e^{-s(\alpha y - \lambda x)}}{\mu s (b + \eta)^{1/2} (\eta - \lambda)(b - \eta)^{1/2}} d\lambda, \quad (2.7)$$

where

$$\alpha(\lambda) = \sqrt{b + \lambda} \sqrt{b - \lambda} = \alpha_+(\lambda) \alpha_-(\lambda).$$

The corresponding result of the dynamic stress intensity factor in the Laplace transform domain is

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{K}(s) &= \lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \sqrt{2\pi x} \bar{r}_{yz}(x, 0, s) \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{s}(b + \eta)^{1/2}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.8)$$

TRANSIENT ANALYSIS FOR A SEMI-INFINITE CRACK IN LAYERED MEDIA

Consider a semi-infinite crack in an elastic strip of a layered medium as shown in Fig. 1. At time $t = 0$, a concentrated anti-plane dynamic loading with magnitude p is applied at the crack faces with a distance h from the crack tip. The time dependence of the dynamic loading is represented by the Heaviside step function $H(t)$. In this problem, the cylindrical wave induced from the dynamic concentrated loading and the diffracted waves generated from the crack tip will be reflected from horizontal interface boundaries, these waves will interact with the crack at some later time. The major difficulty in analyzing this problem will be the one that deals with the interaction of reflected waves with the semi-infinite crack and the superposition technique of the fundamental solutions in the Laplace transform domain will be used. The transient solutions are composed of incident field, reflected field and diffracted field, which will be denoted by superscripts of i , r and d , respectively. Before the time that the i and d waves reflected from the interface boundary of the strip, the problem can be considered as a semi-infinite crack in an unbounded medium.

The incident field of the cylindrical wave generated by the concentrated loading expressed in the Laplace transform domain can be obtained as follows

$$\bar{r}_{yz}(x, 0, s) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_\lambda} -p e^{s\lambda(x+h)} d\lambda. \quad (3.1)$$

The applied traction on the crack face as indicated in (3.1), has the functional form $e^{s\lambda x}$. Since the solutions of applying traction $e^{s\eta x}$ on crack faces have been solved in Section 2, the diffracted field generated from the stationary semi-infinite crack can be constructed by superimposing the incident wave traction that is equal to (3.1). When we combine (2.5) and (3.1), the solution of diffracted wave in the Laplace transform domain can be expressed as follows:

$$\bar{r}_{yz}^d(x, y, s) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_\lambda} -p \left\{ \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\Gamma_{\eta_2}} \frac{(b_1 + \eta_2)^{1/2}}{(\lambda - \eta_2)(b_1 + \lambda)^{1/2}} e^{s\lambda h} e^{-s(\alpha y - \eta_2 x)} d\eta_2 \right\} d\lambda. \quad (3.2)$$

By using the Cagniard-de Hoop method of Laplace inversion, the incident diffracted and stress fields in time domain is obtained as follows

$$r_{yz}^i(x, y, t) = \frac{-pt \sin \theta}{\pi r (t^2 - b_1^2 r^2)^{1/2}} H(t - b_1 r), \quad (3.3)$$

$$\tau_{yz}^d(x, y, t) = \frac{p}{2\pi^2} \int_{b_1, h}^{t-b_1 r_2} \operatorname{Re} \left[H(\eta_1^+, \eta_2^+) \frac{\partial \eta_1^+}{\partial t_1} \frac{\partial \eta_2^+}{\partial t_2} - H(\eta_1^-, \eta_2^+) \frac{\partial \eta_1^-}{\partial t_1} \frac{\partial \eta_2^+}{\partial t_2} \right] dt_1, \quad (3.4)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_1^\pm &= -\frac{t_1}{h} \pm i\epsilon, \\ \eta_2^\pm &= -\frac{t_2}{r_2} \cos \theta_2 \pm i \left(\frac{t_2^2}{r_2^2} - b_1^2 \right)^{1/2} \sin \theta_2, \\ r &= ((x+h)^2 + y^2)^{1/2}, \quad \theta = \cos^{-1}[(x+h)/r], \\ r_2 &= (x^2 + y^2)^{1/2}, \quad \theta_2 = \cos^{-1}(x/r_2), \\ H(\eta_1, \eta_2) &= \frac{(b_1 + \eta_2)^{1/2}}{(\eta_1 - \eta_2)(b_1 + \eta_1)^{1/2}}, \\ t &= t_1 + t_2. \end{aligned}$$

The corresponding dynamic stress intensity factor induced by diffracted wave expressed in time domain will be

$$K^s(t) = p \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi h}} H(t - b_1 h). \quad (3.5)$$

The dynamic stress intensity factor shown in (3.5) jump from zero at the instant that the cylindrical wave generated by the concentrated loading reach the crack tip.

After some later time, the incident wave (*i* wave) generated from the dynamic concentrated loading and the diffracted wave (*d* wave) radiated out from the crack will be reflected from the interface which will be indicated as the *ir* and *dr* wave, respectively. The solutions for reflected waves generated from the interface expressed in the Laplace transform domain can be obtained as follows

$$\bar{\tau}_{yz}^{ir+dr}(x, y, s) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int \int \frac{\gamma_{1/2}(\eta_2) p \alpha_+(\eta_2)}{(\eta_1 - \eta_2) \alpha_+(\eta_1)} e^{s h \eta_1} e^{s \alpha_1 (y-2l) + s \eta_2 x} d\eta_2 d\eta_1, \quad (3.6)$$

where

$$\gamma_{1/2} = \frac{\mu_1 \alpha_1 - \mu_2 \alpha_2}{\mu_1 \alpha_1 + \mu_2 \alpha_2}.$$

The induced dynamic stress intensity factor by *ir* and *dr* waves can be obtained by setting $y = 0$ in (3.6) and the fundamental solution expressed in (2.8). The result for the stress intensity factor expressed in the Laplace transform domain will have the following form

$$\bar{K}^{ir+dr}(s) = \frac{-1}{4\pi^2} \int \int \frac{p \sqrt{2} \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_2)}{\sqrt{s}(\eta_1 - \eta_2) \alpha_+(\eta_1)} e^{s h \eta_1 - 2s \alpha_1 (\eta_2) l} d\eta_2 d\eta_1. \quad (3.7)$$

The dynamic stress intensity factor expressed in time domain will be

$$K^{ir+dr}(t) = \frac{\sqrt{2} p}{\pi^{3/2}} \int_{b_1 r_1}^t \frac{1}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} \operatorname{Im} \left\{ \frac{\gamma_{1/2}(\lambda^+) \frac{\partial \lambda^+}{\partial \tau}}{\alpha_+(\lambda^+)} \right\}_{t=\tau} d\tau, \quad (3.8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^+ &= \frac{t_1 \cos \theta_1}{r_1} + i \frac{\sin \theta_1}{r_1} \sqrt{t_1^2 - b_1^2 r_1^2}, \\ r_1 &= [h^2 + (2l)^2]^{1/2}, \\ \theta_1 &= \cos^{-1}(-h/r_1), \end{aligned}$$

and

$$K^{drd}(t) = \frac{-p\sqrt{2}}{\pi^{5/2}} \int_{b_1 h + 2b_1 l}^t \int_{b_1 h}^{r-2b_1 l} \frac{1}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{\gamma_{1/2}(\eta_2^+)}{\alpha_+(\eta_1^+)(\eta_1^+ - \eta_2^+)} \frac{\partial \eta_1^+}{\partial t_1} \frac{\partial \eta_2^+}{\partial t_2} \right]_{t=\tau} dt_1 d\tau, \quad (3.9)$$

where

$$\eta_1^\pm = -\frac{t}{h} \pm i\epsilon,$$

$$\eta_2^\pm = \pm i \sqrt{\frac{t^2}{4l^2} - b_1^2},$$

$$t_1 + t_2 = t.$$

Finally, the complete transient solutions for dynamic stress intensity factor that account for the contributions of all the reflected and diffracted waves are finally obtained explicitly. The solutions can be simplified into a very compact form as follows

$$K(t) = K^0(t) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} 2K^m(t) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^n k^{0,n}(t) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^{n+1} K^{m,n}(t), \quad (3.10)$$

where

$$K^0(t) = p \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi h}} H(t - b_1 h), \quad (3.11)$$

$$K^m(t) = \frac{p\sqrt{2}}{\pi^{3/2}} \int_{b_1 r_m}^t \frac{1}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} \operatorname{Im} \left\{ \frac{[\gamma_{1/2}(\eta_{1,m}^+)]^m \partial \eta_{1,m}^+}{\alpha_+(\eta_{1,m}^+)} \frac{\partial}{\partial t_1} \right\}_{t_1=\tau} d\tau, \quad (3.12)$$

$$K^{m,n}(t) = \frac{2p\sqrt{2}i^q}{\sqrt{\pi}(2\pi i)^{n+1}} \int_{b_1 r_m + 2nb_1 l}^t \int_{b_1 r_m}^{a_1} \int_{2b_1 l}^{a_2} \int_{2b_1 l}^{a_3} \dots \int_{2b_1 l}^{a_n} \frac{1}{\sqrt{t-\tau}} \operatorname{SIF}_{m,n} dt_n dt_{n-1} \dots dt_1 d\tau, \quad (3.13)$$

in which

$$a_1 = \tau - 2nb_1 l,$$

$$a_j = \tau - t_1 - t_2 - \dots - t_{j-1} - 2(n-j+1)b_1 l, \quad j = 2, 3, \dots, n$$

$$q = 0 \quad \text{when } n = 1, 3, 5, \dots; \quad q = 1 \quad \text{when } n = 2, 4, 6, \dots$$

$$\operatorname{SIF}_{m,n} = \operatorname{Re} \left[\frac{[\gamma_{1/2}(\eta_{1,m}^\pm)]^m \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_2^\pm) \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_3^\pm) \dots \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_{n+1}^\pm) (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_{1,m}^\pm}{\partial t_1}) \dots (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_n^\pm}{\partial t_n}) (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_{n+1}^\pm}{\partial t_{n+1}})}{\alpha_+(\eta_{1,m}^\pm)(\eta_{1,m}^\pm - \eta_2^\pm)(\eta_2^\pm - \eta_3^\pm) \dots (\eta_{n-1}^\pm - \eta_n^\pm)(\eta_n^\pm - \eta_{n+1}^\pm)} \right]_{t=\tau},$$

for $n = 1, 3, 5, \dots$

$$\operatorname{SIF}_{m,n} = \operatorname{Im} \left[\frac{[\gamma_{1/2}(\eta_{1,m}^\pm)]^m \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_2^\pm) \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_3^\pm) \dots \gamma_{1/2}(\eta_{n+1}^\pm) (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_{1,m}^\pm}{\partial t_1}) \dots (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_n^\pm}{\partial t_n}) (\pm \frac{\partial \eta_{n+1}^\pm}{\partial t_{n+1}})}{\alpha_+(\eta_{1,m}^\pm)(\eta_{1,m}^\pm - \eta_2^\pm)(\eta_2^\pm - \eta_3^\pm) \dots (\eta_{n-1}^\pm - \eta_n^\pm)(\eta_n^\pm - \eta_{n+1}^\pm)} \right]_{t=\tau},$$

for $n = 2, 4, 6, \dots$

$$\eta_{1,m}^{\pm} = \frac{t_1 \cos \theta_m}{r_m} \pm i \frac{\sin \theta_m}{r_m} \sqrt{t_1^2 - b_1^2 r_m^2},$$

$$r_m = [h^2 + (2ml)^2]^{1/2}; \quad \theta_m = \cos^{-1}(-h/r_m),$$

$$\eta_j^{\pm} = \pm i \sqrt{\frac{t_j^2}{4l^2} - b_1^2}, \quad j = 2, 3, 4, \dots$$

$$t_j = t - t_1 - t_2 - \dots - t_{j-1}, \quad j = 2, 3, 4, \dots$$

$$\gamma_{1/2}(\eta) = \frac{\mu_1 \alpha_1(\eta) - \mu_2 \alpha_2(\eta)}{\mu_1 \alpha_1(\eta) + \mu_2 \alpha_2(\eta)},$$

$$\alpha_1(\eta) = \alpha_+(\eta) \alpha_-(\eta) = \sqrt{b_1 + \eta} \sqrt{b_1 - \eta},$$

$$\alpha_2(\eta) = \sqrt{b_2 + \eta} \sqrt{b_2 - \eta}.$$

The dynamic stress intensity factors for various situation are shown in Figs. 2-7. Fig. 2 shows the dynamic stress intensity factor for $\mu_2/\mu_1 = 0$, which is the case for a semi-infinite crack in a strip and subjected to traction free boundary conditions. We can see that the transient solution approach to the corresponding static value ($K = p\sqrt{2/\pi l}[1 - e^{-\pi h/l}]^{-1/2}$) after the first few waves has arrived at the crack tip, and the low h/l ratio case approach to the static value faster than that for high h/l ratio. Figs. 3-5 show the transient response of dynamic stress intensity factor for different value of μ_2/μ_1 for $h/l = 0.5, 1$ and 2 , respectively. Fig.6 and Fig. 7 represent the result for different ratio of shear wave speed b_1/b_2 and h/l . It is interesting to note that the lower μ_2/μ_1 ratio cause the higher stress intensity factor, especially during the transient period, and the traction free boundary condition will cause the largest value.

CONCLUSIONS

We have proposed a powerful superposition methodology and a useful fundamental solution is constructed in this study. The fundamental solution is the problem of applying an exponentially distributed traction on the crack face and the solution is determined by superposition of the fundamental solution in the Laplace transform domain. A dynamic loading applied on semi-infinite crack faces in a configuration of layered medium with a strip is investigated. An explicit and complete result of the dynamic stress intensity factor is obtained in closed form and numerical results are evaluated in detail. The numerical results show that the stress intensity factors induced by reflected waves from the interface are significant.

There still have many unanswered questions in dynamic fracture and this work may provide a useful technique for further investigation in more complicated dynamic fracture problems especially on the crack propagation event. The proposed method in this study has already been extended to solve more difficult inplane problem of crack propagation with boundary effect, the results will be shown in a future paper.

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Fig. 1 Configuration and coordinate systems of a crack in a layered medium.

Fig. 2 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for traction free boundary condition $\mu_2/\mu_1 = 0$.

Fig. 3 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for different ratio of shear modulus for $h/l = 0.5$.

Fig. 4 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for different ratio of shear modulus for $h/l = 1$.

Fig. 5 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for different ratio of shear modulus for $h/l = 2$.

Fig. 6 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for different ratio of shear wave speed for $\mu_2/\mu_1 = 0.5$.

Fig. 7 Transient response of the dynamic stress intensity factor for different ratio of shear wave speed for $\mu_2/\mu_1 = 2$.